

1 **Characterizing uncertainty in deep convection triggering**
2 **using explainable machine learning**

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6 ABSTRACT: Realistically representing deep atmospheric convection is important for accurate
7 numerical weather and climate simulations. However, parameterizing where and when deep
8 convection occurs (“triggering”) is a well-known source of model uncertainty. Most triggers pa-
9 rameterize convection deterministically, without considering the uncertainty in the convective state
10 as a stochastic process. In this study, we develop a machine learning model, a random forest, that
11 predicts the probability of deep convection, and then apply clustering of SHAP values, an explain-
12 able machine learning method, to characterize the uncertainty of convective events. The model
13 uses observed large-scale atmospheric variables from the Atmospheric Radiation Measurement
14 constrained variational analysis dataset over the Southern Great Plains, US. The analysis of feature
15 importance shows which mechanisms driving convection are most important, with large-scale verti-
16 cal velocity providing the highest predictive power for more certain, or easier to predict, convective
17 events, followed by the dynamic generation rate of dilute convective available potential energy.
18 Predictions of uncertain convective events instead rely more on other features such as precipitable
19 water or low-level temperature. The model outperforms conventional convective triggers. This
20 suggests that probabilistic machine learning models can be used as stochastic parameterizations to
21 improve the occurrence of convection in weather and climate models in the future.

22 SIGNIFICANCE STATEMENT: Convective storms, which produce clouds and precipitation,
23 are difficult to represent in models since they occur at scales smaller than a model grid box. The
24 purpose of this study is to better understand why convection is sometimes easier or harder to
25 predict with certainty. This is important because predicting where and when convection occurs in
26 atmospheric models affects the energy, moisture, and momentum processes in these models, which
27 is known to lead to errors in weather forecasts and climate projections. This work highlights the
28 importance of representing uncertainty in processes like convection.

29 **1. Introduction**

30 Atmospheric convection plays a crucial role in Earth’s climate system. By transporting mass
31 and energy from the surface to the tropopause, convection impacts the global water, energy, and
32 momentum budgets (Plant and Yano 2015). Convection also produces clouds that affect the
33 radiation budget (Jones et al. 2023; Hartmann 2016). Severe weather events linked to atmospheric
34 convection can result in substantial socioeconomic impacts such as loss of lives and property. It is
35 therefore essential to represent convection accurately in atmospheric simulations.

36 To explicitly resolve individual convective cells and their intracloud motions, atmospheric models
37 need to have a minimum spatial resolution on the order of 100 m (Bryan et al. 2003), but most
38 present-day global atmospheric models range from a resolution of about 10-100 km. Additionally,
39 convection can occur on the timescale of minutes, but most climate models have a timestep on the
40 order of 10 minutes (Cui et al. 2021; Christensen and Zanna 2022). Higher resolution, kilometer-
41 scale global models under development can resolve larger-scale convective storm structures (e.g.,
42 Hohenegger et al. (2023)), but these simulations will not be practical in the near future for
43 operational climate projections with multiple runs given computational limits.

44 Since convection temporal and spatial scales are much smaller than most present-day general cir-
45 culation model (GCM) scales, convection cannot be explicitly resolved, so it is instead represented
46 with a convection parameterization scheme. An important part of the convection parameterization
47 scheme is the triggering of the convection parameterization, which determines where and when
48 convection occurs in the model. Here, the “convective trigger” represents the activation of the
49 convection parameterization in a model grid box from the Eulerian perspective. This study treats
50 triggering similarly to most current convective trigger functions, which do not consider the history

51 of convection and thus do not differentiate between different stages of the convection life cycle
52 (Suhas and Zhang 2014). Generally, the basis of the trigger function is that convectively unstable
53 air in the lower part of the atmosphere under certain atmospheric conditions can trigger convection
54 in the model (Suhas and Zhang 2014). For example, in the NCAR Community Atmosphere Model,
55 version 5 (CAM5), deep convection is triggered when the dilute convective available potential
56 energy (dilute CAPE) exceeds a threshold of 70 J kg^{-1} (Cui et al. 2021).

57 Since the large-scale atmospheric processes that lead to the triggering of convection are not well
58 understood, different weather and climate models use various convective trigger functions (Suhas
59 and Zhang 2014). The primary differences between different convective trigger functions are how
60 the source layer of convection is chosen within the troposphere and how the function realizes the
61 atmospheric instability for convection development (Suhas and Zhang 2014). To initiate the release
62 of the convective instability, some parameterization schemes use the grid-scale vertical velocity
63 (e.g., Kain and Fritsch (1990); Bechtold et al. (2001)). Other models use boundary layer moisture
64 convergence (Tiedtke 1989), or the amount of convective available potential energy (CAPE) as in
65 Zhang and McFarlane (1995). Xie and Zhang (2000) improved upon the CAPE trigger by adding a
66 second condition, the dynamic generation rate of CAPE from large-scale advection (dCAPE). Xie
67 et al. (2019) further modified dCAPE with an unrestricted parcel launch level (dCAPE ULL) to
68 capture nocturnal elevated convection. Another modification of the CAPE trigger was the inclusion
69 of entrainment in the calculation of CAPE (dilute CAPE) by Neale et al. (2008), which improved
70 the simulation of El Niño Southern Oscillation.

71 While there is a general understanding that local-scale convective instabilities cause convection,
72 it is still difficult to map these local processes to coarser GCM scales in space and time. Despite
73 various developments of the convective trigger function over the past several decades, the accurate
74 prediction of the onset time, location and evolution of convection continues to be a challenge in
75 atmospheric models. Many convective triggers activate convection too often, resulting in models
76 producing more drizzling rain than observations (Suhas and Zhang 2014). Errors in the convection
77 trigger function have also been linked to inadequate simulations of the diurnal cycle of convection,
78 the Madden-Julian oscillation, and the ITCZ seasonal migration and double peak biases (Suhas
79 and Zhang 2014). Even with recent improvements, such as using the dynamic generation rate of

80 CAPE (dCAPE) instead of CAPE for the convection trigger, there are still biases in the diurnal
81 cycle and precipitation intensity compared to observations (Cui et al. 2021).

82 One promising approach for improving the representation of convection in atmospheric models
83 is stochastic parameterizations. Since a given large-scale atmospheric state could correspond to
84 multiple sub-grid convective (or non-convective) states, representing the occurrence of sub-grid
85 convection as a stochastic process is a natural choice. Furthermore, stochastic parameterization
86 of the convective trigger will become increasingly important as the spatial resolution of models
87 increases and the scale separation between the large-scale and sub-grid processes decreases; the
88 assumption that each model grid box contains an ensemble of randomly distributed convective
89 plumes is no longer valid (Berner et al. 2017). A few studies have specifically focused on
90 stochasticity of the convection trigger by adding a probabilistic component to a conventional
91 trigger (Bright and Mullen 2002; Song et al. 2007; Rochetin et al. 2014). In a different study, the
92 implementation of a stochastic deep convection parameterization scheme in NCAR CAM5 resulted
93 in improved precipitation frequency (Wang et al. 2016).

94 Another direction for improving the convective trigger function is the application of machine
95 learning (ML) to learn nonlinear relationships directly from observations. Machine learning
96 is particularly well-suited to the convective trigger since the trigger function can easily learn a
97 threshold for when to activate convection from observations. In contrast to conventional convective
98 trigger functions which often use just one or two atmospheric state variables (e.g., vertical velocity,
99 moisture), a ML trigger function can incorporate multiple different dynamic and thermodynamic
100 variables to predict the occurrence of convection for a broader range of meteorological regimes.
101 The inputs and models that perform best are useful in determining which physical assumptions are
102 most accurate; using ML to develop a trigger can inform us about the physics of convection. In
103 addition, since ML algorithms can predict a probability instead of a binary outcome, a ML trigger
104 could be applied as a stochastic trigger parameterization in an operational model.

105 Both ML and stochastic parameterization methods can be used in combination, creating pa-
106 rameterizations that better represent the uncertainty learned from observations or high-resolution
107 datasets (Christensen et al. 2024). For example, Nadiga et al. (2022) use a generative adversarial
108 network, a probabilistic ML method, to generate vertical tendency profiles of temperature and
109 humidity given the large scale atmospheric state from reanalysis. Behrens et al. (2024) apply

110 various stochastic ML approaches to parameterize sub-grid convection and turbulence from a
111 superparameterization embedded in a GCM.

112 Few studies have specifically focused on using ML for the convective trigger. Ukkonen and
113 Mäkelä (2019) applied several ML methods to predict the occurrence of thunderstorms in Europe
114 and Sri Lanka using ERA5 atmospheric reanalysis and lightning datasets. Zhang et al. (2021)
115 applied gradient boosted trees to a variational analysis dataset over the Southern Great Plains, US
116 and the Brazilian Amazon to predict the occurrence of convection. Chen et al. (2023) applied a
117 convolutional neural network to ERA5 reanalysis and TRMM satellite precipitation to predict the
118 occurrence of convection with location-awareness. However, none of the studies consider the ML
119 models within a probabilistic framework to characterize the uncertainty in predicting the occurrence
120 of convection, which is particularly important as models approach the gray zone (Christensen and
121 Zanna 2022).

122 This study aims to improve the understanding of sources of uncertainty in deep convective
123 triggering to ultimately improve the representation of convection in weather and climate models
124 with parameterized convection. A ML model is used to predict the probability of the occurrence
125 of convection, and explainable ML methods are used to understand the uncertainty of convection
126 triggering. The ML model, a random forest, is trained on observed large-scale atmospheric
127 variables from the Atmospheric Radiation Measurement (ARM) constrained variational analysis
128 over the Southern Great Plains observational site. This approach builds off of Zhang et al. (2021),
129 but within a probabilistic framework which incorporates the aleatoric uncertainty in modeling
130 convection occurrence. The model is evaluated against the observed time series of convection,
131 the diurnal cycle, and the reliability of the probability of occurrence. To make the random forest
132 explainable, the relative importance of each feature is used to assess which environmental factors are
133 most closely linked to the occurrence of convection. The contribution of each of the environmental
134 features to the predicted probabilities are then used to cluster the convective events and characterize
135 certain and uncertain convective regimes.

136 We present the dataset and ML methods in Section 2. The main results are presented in Section
137 3, including the ML trigger skill and uncertainty analysis. In Section 4, we discuss the results and
138 implications for weather and climate modeling. Finally, Section 5 concludes with a summary of
139 the study.

140 **2. Methods**

141 *a. Data*

142 The ML model in this study is developed using inputs from observed large-scale atmospheric
143 variables from the Atmospheric Radiation Measurement (ARM) constrained variational analysis
144 dataset (Tang et al. 2019). This study focuses on a dataset from the Southern Great Plains
145 (SGP) observational site, in Oklahoma, US, shown in Figure 1. The SGP site is a multi-decade
146 observatory that has surface meteorological observation stations, eddy flux towers, microwave
147 radiometer stations, and solar and infrared observing stations (Tang et al. 2019). The observations
148 are used in combination with geostationary satellite products, a gridded precipitation product,
149 and Rapid Update Cycle (RUC, before 2012)/Rapid Refresh (RAP, after 2012) numerical weather
150 reanalysis products (Tang et al. 2019). In the variational analysis method, the atmospheric state
151 variables from the reanalysis are constrained by the observed surface and top of atmosphere fluxes
152 (Tang et al. 2019). The variational analysis dataset is particularly useful for the application of a ML
153 trigger because, unlike most reanalysis products, the dataset is dynamically and thermodynamically
154 consistent with the observed fluxes including precipitation.

155 FIG. 1. Domain for the Southern Great Plains variational analysis, outlined by the yellow polygon, located in
156 central US (domain boundary adapted from Tang et al., 2019). RGB image is from GOES-R Advanced Baseline
157 Imager on 2017-08-18, using the 0.45-0.49 μm , 0.59-0.69 μm , and 0.846-0.885 μm wavelength bands (Schmit
158 et al. 2017). Further information on the observational site can be found in Tang et al. (2019).

159 The variational analysis dataset averages the atmospheric state in a region across approximately
160 96-99°W to 35-38°N (Figure 1). The vertical resolution of the dataset is 25 hPa, and the temporal
161 resolution is 1 hour. Inputs from the convectively active summer season (June, July, August) from
162 2004-2018 are used in the model.

163 To define the occurrence of deep convection, a precipitation threshold of 0.5 mm/hr is used,
164 following Suhas and Zhang (2014), Song and Zhang (2017), and Zhang et al. (2021). Using this
165 precipitation threshold is not an exact indicator of convection since there is a lag between when
166 convection initiates and when precipitation occurs. The threshold may also include some stratiform
167 precipitation events. However, this reasonably large precipitation threshold is generally a good
168 indicator of convection over the Southern Great Plains during the summertime (Suhas and Zhang
169 2014). Suhas and Zhang (2014) also tested a range of precipitation thresholds and found that the
170 results of the trigger functions are not sensitive to the threshold value.

171 To predict the occurrence of convection, various dynamic and thermodynamic variables (“fea-
172 tures”) are used in the model (Table 1). Convective processes depend on the atmospheric state
173 near the surface, such as surface temperature, humidity, and sensible and latent heat fluxes, as
174 well as the vertical profiles of atmospheric variables. The features include dilute CAPE, column
175 precipitable water, and large-scale vertical velocity, in addition to those used in Zhang et al. (2021).
176 Since using all vertical levels of the dataset would likely require a more complex ML method to
177 extract relevant convective signals, meaningful scalar features are derived from the vertical column
178 instead. Some atmospheric features, such as temperature and vertical velocity, are averaged across
179 the lower (700-800 hPa), middle (300-700 hPa), and upper (200-300 hPa) levels of the troposphere.
180 Other features, such as convective inhibition (CIN) and dilute CAPE, are indicators of atmospheric
181 stability and are calculated using vertical profiles of temperature and humidity.

182 *b. Machine Learning Trigger*

183 A random forest classifier is used to predict the probability of convection in this study, which is
184 implemented using the Scikit-learn library (Pedregosa et al. 2012). The random forest algorithm
185 is a ML method that averages an ensemble of decision trees (Breiman 2001). Each decision tree
186 is trained on a bootstrapped subset of the dataset, and each decision split is limited to a random
187 subset of the input features (Pedregosa et al. 2012). For a single tree, the predicted probability is

TABLE 1. Input features for the machine learning trigger

Predictors	Abbreviation	Feature Group
Latent heat flux	Latent heat	Srf & Buoyancy
Sensible heat flux	Sensible heat	Srf & Buoyancy
Air temperature at the surface	T surface	Srf & Buoyancy
Air relative humidity at the surface	RH surface	Srf & Buoyancy
Lifting condensation level	LCL	Srf & Buoyancy
Convective inhibition	CIN	Srf & Buoyancy
Dynamic generation of dilute convective available potential energy	dilute dCAPE	Vert. velocity
Vertical velocity in the lower troposphere	ω low	Vert. velocity
Vertical velocity in the middle troposphere	ω mid	Vert. velocity
Vertical velocity in the upper troposphere	ω high	Vert. velocity
Precipitable water in column	PW	Moisture
Specific humidity in the lower troposphere	q low	Moisture
Specific humidity in the middle troposphere	q mid	Moisture
Specific humidity in the upper troposphere	q high	Moisture
Temperature in the lower troposphere	T low	Temperature
Temperature in the middle troposphere	T mid	Temperature
Temperature in the upper troposphere	T high	Temperature
Horizontal advective tendency of specific humidity in the lower troposphere	Adv. q low	Adv. q
Horizontal advective tendency of specific humidity in the middle troposphere	Adv. q mid	Adv. q
Horizontal advective tendency of specific humidity in the upper troposphere	Adv. q high	Adv. q
Horizontal advective tendency of dry static energy in the lower troposphere	Adv. s low	Adv. s
Horizontal advective tendency of dry static energy in the middle troposphere	Adv. s mid	Adv. s
Horizontal advective tendency of dry static energy in the upper troposphere	Adv. s high	Adv. s
Wind shear in the lower troposphere	Shear low	Shear
Wind shear in the middle troposphere	Shear mid	Shear
Wind shear in the upper troposphere	Shear high	Shear

Notes: The lower, middle, and upper troposphere are defined by the pressure levels 700 – 800, 300 – 700, and 200 – 300 hPa, respectively. Table partially adapted from Zhang et al. (2021).

188 the fraction of samples of the same class in a leaf. The probability of convection is calculated as
189 the mean of the predicted probabilities of the trees in the forest (Pedregosa et al. 2012).

190 With random forests, the feature importance is shared, but diluted, among correlated features
191 because of the random selection of features at each node (Breiman 2001). In contrast, other
192 approaches, such as logistic regression or neural networks, can heavily favor one correlated feature
193 over another, or even give correlated features opposite signs (Flora et al. 2024). While multiple ML
194 methods could be suitable, we used a random forest because of its simplicity to train and tune, and

195 because tree-based methods in general can often out-perform other methods like neural networks
196 on tabular-style datasets (Lundberg et al. 2020).

197 The random forest is trained and evaluated using the environmental features from Table 1 to
198 predict the occurrence of convection. The first twelve summers of the dataset (2004-2015; 26,496
199 samples) are used for training, and the last three summers (2016-2018; 6,624 samples) are used for
200 model evaluation. All features are standardized to have a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1
201 before model training. Further details of the random forest hyperparameter optimization are given
202 in Appendix A.

203 The atmospheric features represent the domain-averaged value at a given time, while the corre-
204 sponding precipitation represents the total precipitation from 30 min before to 30 min after that
205 time. The model uses the features to predict the occurrence of convection at the next timestep
206 (hour), i.e. 30 to 90 minutes after the feature variables are valid. This allows the model to learn
207 to predict convection that will happen in the next hour, instead of diagnosing convection that has
208 already happened in the current hour.

209 Both convective and non-convective events at hourly temporal resolution are included as inputs
210 to train the model. In the original dataset, the number of non-convective events (majority class) far
211 outnumbers the number of convective events (minority class), with a convective to non-convective
212 ratio of 0.095. To reduce the class imbalance and optimize training, the majority class was randomly
213 undersampled by a factor of $1/r$. Since the dataset was resampled, the frequency of convective
214 events will be different in the undersampled dataset compared to the original dataset (Miloshevich
215 et al. 2023). Thus, the raw probabilities predicted from the undersampled dataset were adjusted to
216 evaluate skill using the original dataset (Miloshevich et al. 2023). A more detailed explanation of
217 the undersampling and probability scaling is given in Appendix B.

218 The ML trigger is designed similarly to convection triggers in operational models; it identifies
219 convection occurrence at every timestep, including both the initiation and persistence of convection.
220 Thus, the trigger must be designed to capture all occurrences of convection due to large-scale
221 upward motion associated with processes such as synoptic-scale systems, existing convection, sub
222 grid-scale dynamic instability, or growth of the boundary layer (Xie et al. 2004).

223 *c. Evaluation Metrics*

224 To evaluate the model skill, various scores are used to compare the probabilistic random forest
225 to deterministic conventional triggers. For a deterministic comparison, precision (also known as
226 success ratio), recall (also known as probability of detection), and the F1 score are applied to
227 the minority class (convective events). These evaluation metrics emphasize the performance on
228 the minority class, which allows for a more nuanced evaluation given the imbalanced dataset. To
229 compare the ML trigger to deterministic triggers, we assume a binary outcome of the random
230 forest, where probabilities greater than 0.47 are convective events. The threshold of 0.47 ensures
231 that the observed frequency of convection matches the predicted frequency. Precision (P) is the
232 percentage of true positives (TP) over the total of the predicted positive cases (true positives (TP)
233 plus false positives (FP)):

$$P = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}. \quad (1)$$

234 Recall (R) is the percentage of true positives (TP) over the total of the true positive cases (true
235 positives (TP) plus false negatives (FN)):

$$R = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}. \quad (2)$$

236 The F1 score incorporates skill in both overprediction and underprediction, and is equal to the
237 harmonic mean of precision and recall:

$$F1 = \frac{2PR}{P + R}. \quad (3)$$

238 The F1 score optimally has a perfect value of one, and it is closer to one when both precision and
239 recall are high.

240 While precision, recall and F1 scores are deterministic scores, the triggers are additionally
241 evaluated in a probabilistic framework with the Brier Skill Score (BSS),

$$BSS = 1 - \frac{BS}{BS_{ref}} \quad (4)$$

242 where BS is the Brier score for each trigger and is BS_{ref} the reference Brier score. The Brier score
 243 is defined as

$$BS = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (p_i - o_i)^2 \quad (5)$$

244 where p_i are the predicted probabilities of convection and o_i are the observed occurrences of
 245 convection, summed over the size of the dataset, n . The reference Brier score, BS_{ref} , uses the
 246 average frequency of observed convection during each hour of the day as the predicted probabilities.
 247 The BSS has a perfect value of one but can be negative if the predicted probabilities are worse
 248 than the reference. The BSS for the deterministic triggers are also calculated with Equation 4
 249 but using the binary predicted convection occurrences instead of probabilities. In contrast to the
 250 deterministic scores, the BSS is not as sensitive to the minority class for an imbalanced dataset.

251 *d. Conventional Trigger Functions*

252 The random forest was also evaluated against four conventional CAPE-based trigger functions:
 253 CAPE, dilute CAPE, the dynamic generation rate of CAPE, and the dynamic generation rate of
 254 dilute CAPE. These trigger functions were tested on observations along with various other trigger
 255 functions by Suhas and Zhang (2014) and Song and Zhang (2017), who found that the dynamic
 256 generation rate of dilute dCAPE had the best performance. In this study, all four trigger functions
 257 use pseudo-adiabatic parcels that ascend from the most unstable pressure level in the atmosphere
 258 below 600 hPa, known as the unrestricted launch level (Xie et al. 2019). Allowing the parcels to
 259 launch from above the boundary layer helps to capture elevated nocturnal convection (Xie et al.
 260 2019).

261 Convectively available potential energy (CAPE) is defined as the vertical integral of a parcel's
 262 buoyancy from the level of free convection to the level of neutral buoyancy,

$$CAPE = - \int_{\ln p_{LFC}}^{\ln p_{LNB}} R_d (T_{v, parcel} - T_{v, env}) d \ln p \quad (6)$$

263 where R_d is the gas constant for dry air, p_{LNB} is the pressure at the level of neutral buoyancy, p_{LFC} is
 264 the pressure at the level of free convection, $T_{v, parcel}$ is the virtual temperature of parcel, and $T_{v, env}$
 265 is the virtual temperature of environmental air. Originally developed for the Zhang-McFarlane
 266 scheme (Zhang and McFarlane 1995), CAPE-based triggers have been used in models such as

267 the NCAR CAM model, WRF, and the US Department of Energy E3SM Atmosphere Model. In
 268 models, when CAPE exceeds a threshold, typically 70 J kg^{-1} , the convection parameterization
 269 scheme is activated.

270 Xie and Zhang (2000) improved the CAPE trigger by developing dCAPE, which is the dynamic
 271 generation rate of CAPE from large-scale advection. dCAPE is calculated by

$$dCAPE = \frac{CAPE[T + \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \delta t, q + \frac{\partial q}{\partial t} \delta t] - CAPE[T, q]}{\delta t} \quad (7)$$

272 where $\frac{\partial T}{\partial t}$ is the advective tendency of temperature due to large-scale advection, $\frac{\partial q}{\partial t}$ is the advective
 273 tendency of specific humidity due to large-scale advection, and δt is the timestep (1 hr). In
 274 operational models, when dCAPE exceeds a threshold, typically $65 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ hr}^{-1}$, the convection
 275 parameterization scheme is activated.

276 The advective tendency of temperature is defined as the sum of the horizontal advective tendency
 277 (a), the vertical advective tendency (b), and the adiabatic expansion term (c),

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \underbrace{-\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla T}_{(a)} - \underbrace{\omega \frac{\partial T}{\partial p}}_{(b)} + \underbrace{\frac{\omega}{c_p \rho}}_{(c)} \quad (8)$$

278 where \mathbf{u} is the horizontal velocity vector, ω is the vertical velocity, c_p is the specific heat capacity
 279 of air, and ρ is the air density. The advective tendency of temperature is also equivalent to the
 280 advective tendency of dry static energy, which is sometime used instead in the definition of dCAPE
 281 (e.g., Song and Zhang (2018)).

282 The advective tendency of specific humidity is defined as the sum of the horizontal advective
 283 tendency and the vertical advective tendency,

$$\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} = -\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla q - \omega \frac{\partial q}{\partial p}. \quad (9)$$

284 Neale et al. (2008) also improved the CAPE trigger by incorporating entrainment into the CAPE
 285 calculation (dilute CAPE). When a parcel ascends, its entropy (S) follows the equation

$$\frac{\partial mS}{\partial z} = \frac{\partial m}{\partial z} \bar{S} = \varepsilon \bar{S} \quad (10)$$

286 where m is the parcel mass, and \bar{S} is the environment entropy. The entrainment rate, ε , is set to
287 10^{-3} m^{-1} . As the parcel ascends, its entropy is updated with dilution, and then the temperature and
288 humidity at each level is obtained. In models, when dilute CAPE exceeds a threshold, typically 70
289 J kg^{-1} , the convection parameterization scheme is activated.

290 The fourth trigger function is dilute dCAPE, which combines the dynamic generation rate from
291 advection (Equation 7) with the entrainment calculation (Equation 10). The threshold used is the
292 same for dCAPE, $65 \text{ J kg}^{-1}\text{hr}^{-1}$.

293 To fairly compare the CAPE-based triggers to the ML trigger, values across the range of each
294 CAPE-based trigger were tested as thresholds. For each trigger, the threshold with the highest
295 F1 score on the same training set used for the random forest was chosen, and then the optimized
296 threshold was used for evaluation on the test set. The optimized thresholds for CAPE, dilute
297 CAPE, dCAPE, and dilute dCAPE were 259 J kg^{-1} , 65 J kg^{-1} , $141 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ hr}^{-1}$, and 66 J kg^{-1}
298 hr^{-1} , respectively. The optimized thresholds differ significantly from the operational thresholds
299 (70 J kg^{-1} , 70 J kg^{-1} , $65 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ hr}^{-1}$, and $65 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ hr}^{-1}$, respectively), possibly because they are
300 optimized on a single location and season instead of a full global model.

301 *e. Explainable Machine Learning Methods*

302 To explain the random forest predictions, we used feature importance methods, which estimate
303 the impact on model performance, and feature relevance methods, which estimate the impact on
304 the predicted probabilities (Flora et al. 2024). For feature relevance, we used SHapley Additive
305 exPlanations (SHAP) calculated using KernelSHAP from Lundberg and Lee (2017). A SHAP value
306 represents the marginal contribution of a feature to a prediction while considering all permutations
307 of features (Lundberg and Lee 2017). For an event, the SHAP values of each feature sum to
308 the difference between the expected probability and the predicted probability. Individual SHAP
309 values can be positive or negative, indicating the random forest judges the given feature to lead to a
310 more or less likely chance of convection, respectively. They are particularly useful for explainable
311 ML because they provide both local (individual sample) and global (average across all features or
312 samples) information about how the model works. The average magnitude of the SHAP value of
313 each feature gives a global metric for feature relevance.

314 For feature importance, we used SAGE values, which estimate the global impact of features
315 on model performance using the test set. SAGE values are calculated in a similar way to SHAP
316 values, except the impact is measured with model performance instead of the model output (Covert
317 et al. 2020). We also compared the SAGE feature importance to impurity feature importance,
318 which is based on the average decrease in impurity when a feature is used to split a leaf in the
319 trees in the random forest (Breiman 2001). In addition, we also compared single-pass permutation
320 feature importance, which is proportional to the magnitude of the decrease in model skill when
321 data corresponding to a single feature is randomly shuffled (Breiman 2001). The single-pass
322 permutation feature importance was evaluated on the F1 score of the test set.

323 Since the random forest can dilute feature importance and relevance among correlated features,
324 we also grouped the features into correlated groups, which are defined in Table 1. The grouped
325 SAGE and SHAP rankings are calculated by summing the SAGE and SHAP values for the features
326 in each group (Flora et al. 2024). This approach helps capture the collective effects of correlated
327 features on the model (Flora et al. 2024).

328 *f. Clustering into Convective Regimes*

329 After the random forest is trained on the inputs, the SHAP values for each individual sample
330 and feature is clustered using k-means clustering from the Scikit-learn ML library for Python
331 (Pedregosa et al. 2012). Following a method similar to Douglas and Stier (2024), clustering with
332 SHAP values produces convective triggering regimes controlled by a similar combination of input
333 features. Instead of clustering the original feature values, clustering the SHAP values allows for the
334 interpretation to focus on the contribution of each feature to the predicted convection probabilities.
335 To determine the optimal number of clusters, the elbow method was used (Kodinariya and Makwana
336 2013), in which the within-cluster variance is plotted against the number of clusters. The number
337 of clusters used in this study, $n=6$, was chosen where the decline in variance flattens with increasing
338 number of clusters. More details on the elbow method are shown in Appendix C. The clusters
339 from the SHAP values were then interpreted in terms of the model inputs and the uncertainty in the
340 predicted probabilities. Since the SHAP values correspond to the unscaled predicted probabilities,
341 the probabilities from the random forest were not scaled for the clustering analysis.

342 **3. Results**

343 *a. Random Forest Convection Trigger Skill*

344 The random forest trigger was trained to predict the probability of convection, and then its skill
345 was evaluated and compared to conventional CAPE-based triggers. The skill of the random forest
346 is first evaluated on the test set using precision, recall, and F1 scores. On the full, unbalanced test
347 dataset after the probability scaling, which is similar to the original observed dataset, the precision,
348 recall and F1 scores were 0.77, 0.73, and 0.75, respectively. Since the precision is higher than the
349 recall, the model tends to underpredict convective events; there were slightly fewer false positives
350 than false negatives.

351 In contrast to the deterministic scores that assume a binary output from the random forest, the
352 BSS evaluates the random forest probabilities directly. On the full, unbalanced test dataset after
353 the probability scaling the BSS is 0.47.

354 A reliability diagram can also be used to evaluate the predicted probabilities without transforming
355 them into a binary output. Figure 2 shows how well the predicted probabilities from the random
356 forest match the observed frequency of convection occurrence. The probabilities that were adjusted
357 using the probability scaling are closer to a perfect reliability curve, because the probability scaling
358 systematically reduces the probability assigned to convective events. Figure 2 also shows the
359 marginal totals, which represent the distribution of sample sizes of the predicted probabilities.
360 Most events are predicted as having near-zero probabilities.

366 *b. Diurnal Cycle and Comparison to Conventional Trigger Functions*

367 The random forest trigger was compared to the conventional triggers using both deterministic
368 and probabilistic evaluation metrics. Figure 3 shows a comparison for precision, recall, F1, and
369 BSS. The random forest outperforms all of the CAPE-based conventional triggers for precision,
370 F1 and BSS. While CAPE and dilute CAPE have high recall because they tend to overpredict
371 convection, the overpredictions also cause much lower precision, F1 and BSS. CAPE and dilute
372 CAPE have negative BSS, indicating they perform worse than the baseline hourly diurnal frequency
373 of observed convection. While the random forest trigger performs better than the conventional
374 triggers for the deterministic metrics, it performs particularly well for the probabilistic metric, the
375 BSS, since the random forest itself is probabilistic.

354 FIG. 2. Reliability curve for the random forest, before (blue line) and after (green line) the probability scaling.
 355 The reliability curve after the probability scaling is closer to a perfect reliability curve (black dashed line),
 356 indicating that the probability scaling makes the predictions more reliable. The histogram in gray shows the
 357 marginal totals, which are the sample sizes of the predicted probabilities in each bin. Most events are predicted
 358 as having near-zero probabilities (note the broken y-axis for histogram sample size).

381 A promising ML trigger needs to simulate the diurnal cycle accurately, since the diurnal cycle
 382 has important impacts on the Earth system, such as different shortwave and net cloud radiative
 383 effects during the night and day. Figure 4 shows the diurnal cycle over the SGP for the random
 384 forest convection probability in comparison to the observed occurrence of convection and four
 385 CAPE-based triggers. The observed summertime diurnal cycle over the Southern Great Plains
 386 has two peaks in the frequency of convection throughout the day: a peak in the evening, which
 387 is connected to surface heating throughout the day, and a peak in the night/early morning, which
 388 is connected to mesoscale convective systems that propagate from the west (Zhao et al. 2017).
 389 Even with an optimized threshold, CAPE and dilute CAPE are poor predictors of convection
 390 since they overpredict many events. Of the conventional triggers, dCAPE and dilute dCAPE most
 391 closely match the observed diurnal cycle, but have high hour-to-hour variability not seen in the

376 FIG. 3. Comparison of the random forest and conventional triggers for precision, recall, F1, and BSS. For all
 377 evaluation metrics, values closer to 1 are better. The gray bars represent 95% confidence intervals from 1000
 378 bootstrapped trials. The random forest outperforms all conventional triggers for precision, F1 and BSS. While
 379 CAPE and dilute CAPE tend to overpredict convection, leading to high recall, the overpredictions lead to poor
 380 precision and thus poor F1 and BSS overall.

392 observed cycle. Even though dilute dCAPE is found to be better than dCAPE in previous studies,
 393 dilute dCAPE doesn't capture the correct amplitude as well as dCAPE. The random forest slightly
 394 overestimates the observed amplitude, but is also smoother than the dCAPE and dilute dCAPE
 395 triggers, which could be because it is more robust since it is able to consider multiple features. All
 396 of the better-performing triggers capture the nighttime convection, but underpredict the evening
 397 peak in convection. In contrast to conventional trigger functions (Covey et al. 2016; Dai 2006), the
 398 diurnal cycle of the random forest trigger is not early in phase; instead, it is delayed by 1-2 hours
 399 (timesteps).

404 *c. Feature Importance and Relevance*

405 The application of a random forest to the ARM variational analysis can provide feature rankings
 406 to help gain insights into which environmental variables among the variables in the dataset are
 407 most closely linked to convection occurrence. Figure 5 shows the feature rankings using several
 408 feature importance and relevance measures. The different methods give different orderings for
 409 the features. Having different measures is therefore very useful, since comparing them indicates
 410 which conclusions are robust. Even though the details of the ordering can change, the broad picture
 411 shows consistency in the general rankings. Across all the methods, vertical velocity in the mid

400 FIG. 4. Diurnal cycle of convection (local time) for the observations (black), random forest model probability
 401 (green), and four optimized conventional convection trigger frequencies. The left panel shows all convection
 402 triggers, and the right panel shows a zoomed-in plot for the best-performing convective triggers: dCAPE, dilute
 403 dCAPE, and the random forest.

412 troposphere (ω mid) is the dominating environmental variable in predicting convection, followed
 413 by dilute dCAPE. The high predictive value of large-scale vertical velocity is consistent with
 414 known mechanisms of convection triggering, in which upward motion associated with convergence
 415 from large-scale dynamical processes helps convection overcome CIN and reach the level of free
 416 convection. It is also interesting that vertical velocity is found to have more predictive performance
 417 than dilute dCAPE, which was previously found to be the best-performing conventional trigger
 418 function (Suhas and Zhang 2014; Song and Zhang 2017).

419 Several other features, including (in no particular order) vertical velocity in the upper and lower
 420 troposphere, column precipitable water, and surface relative humidity are also important features.
 421 The relative ranking of these features depends on the feature importance method. These features
 422 are generally consistent with previous studies, where surface properties, such as temperature and
 423 humidity, are important in determining the stability of the atmospheric column, and sufficient
 424 moisture throughout the atmospheric column is necessary to drive convection.

425 FIG. 5. Feature rankings show which inputs to the random forest are the most important predictors of convection
 426 for the dataset from the Southern Great Plains observational dataset. (a) Impurity feature importance, (b) single-
 427 pass permutation feature importance, (c) SAGE feature importance, and (d) SHAP feature relevance have similar,
 428 but not the same, feature rankings. The top two most important features for all metrics, in blue text, are ω mid
 429 and dilute dCAPE. Features with higher importance but not the exact same ranking across all three metrics are in
 430 red text. The black bars represent the standard deviation of each feature importance value. The grouped feature
 431 rankings are shown for (e) SAGE and (f) SHAP values.

432 However, since the feature importance methods differ in ranking order because the methods used
433 to measure importance are inherently different, caution should be used in taking any one method
434 as the truth. This dataset provides a good example for why multiple methods should be applied to
435 interpret feature importance results, whereas many previous studies only apply one method.

436 Since correlated features may have diluted feature relevance, the grouped SAGE and SHAP
437 feature rankings are useful in understanding how correlated groups collectively impact the model
438 and compare to other feature groups. In Figure 5, panels e and f, the vertical velocity features are
439 ranked the highest for both SAGE and SHAP. The other important groups are the moisture features
440 and the surface and buoyancy features, but their relative rankings differ for SHAP and SAGE.
441 Overall, the grouped rankings reflect the individual rankings in that vertical velocity features
442 dominate, and surface and moisture-related features follow, but the ranking of any individual
443 method may not be robust.

444 While large-scale vertical velocity can cause convection, it can also be caused by convection. The
445 large-scale vertical velocity in the variational analysis used in this study is more likely to be due to
446 large-scale dynamics, given the large size of the domain (Figure 1), which can contain many small-
447 scale convective updrafts and downdrafts at one time. Conceptually, convection parameterizations
448 do not typically output a vertical velocity tendency, under the assumption that the updrafts balance
449 the downdrafts within a grid column. In addition, in atmospheric models, the convective trigger
450 must be designed to initiate convection for both the start of convective events and persisting
451 convection that may be triggered by previous convection. Thus, regardless of whether vertical
452 velocity is due to large-scale dynamical processes, previous convection, or boundary layer growth,
453 it tends to be a good indicator of convection. This is demonstrated in Figure 6, which shows the
454 average time series of the convective events over the SGP. Many hours before a convective event,
455 vertical velocity tends to be close to zero. In the 1-2 hours leading up to convection, upward
456 vertical velocity begins to increase in magnitude, and then remains high throughout the convection
457 occurrence (note that negative ω indicates upward motion). Dilute dCAPE follows a remarkably
458 similar path to vertical velocity leading up to convection, indicative of a close relationship between
459 dilute dCAPE and vertical velocity, which is investigated further in the following section. Other
460 atmospheric predictors, such as dilute CAPE and CIN, do not show a similar behavior.

461 FIG. 6. Hourly averages (blue lines) and interquartile ranges (blue shaded areas) for various atmospheric
 462 variables before and during a convective event. The top panel shows the convective event, with no convection
 463 until time = 0 hr, and persisting convection afterwards. The black line in the top panel represents the number of
 464 samples averaged over each hour. Vertical velocity (ω mid) and dilute dCAPE show changes in the few hours
 465 leading up to a convective event, but other variables such as dilute CAPE and CIN do not show a similar change.

466 Since dilute dCAPE appears to be the second-most important feature across all importance metrics
 467 and behaves as a precursor to convection in Figure 6, we investigated the physical mechanisms
 468 linking dilute dCAPE and the occurrence of convection. Figure 7d shows the advective tendency
 469 temperature profile which is used to calculate dilute dCAPE, following Equations 7-10, averaged for
 470 the convective and non-convective events. In comparison to non-convective events, the convective
 471 events have a negative total advective tendency of temperature in the middle and upper atmosphere,

472 which decreases the environmental temperature profile, causing a larger temperature difference
 473 from the warmer air parcel, and thus an increase in buoyancy.

474 FIG. 7. Vertical profiles of the terms (a, b, c) that make up the total advective tendency for temperature (d)
 475 following Equation 8, averaged for the convective (blue) and non-convective (orange) events. The adiabatic
 476 expansion term (c) is the largest component of the total tendency, and the adiabatic term is equal to the product of
 477 the vertical velocity (e) and a function of density (f), $1/(c_p \rho)$. The shaded areas represent one standard deviation
 478 from the mean. Note the unequal horizontal scales.

479 In Figure 7, the total advective tendency can be decomposed into the horizontal advection
 480 component (Equation 8, Term a), the vertical advection component (Equation 8, Term b), and a
 481 vertical adiabatic expansion term (Equation 8, Term c). All three terms show differences between

482 convective and non-convective events, but the vertical adiabatic expansion term is the largest in
483 magnitude and contributes the most to the total tendency (Figure 7c, note the unequal horizontal
484 scales). The vertical adiabatic expansion term is a product of a function of density, which is nearly
485 identical for convection and non-convection (Figure 7f), and vertical velocity, which differs for the
486 average convective and non-convective cases (Figure 7e). Therefore, the primary component in
487 dilute dCAPE that makes it a good classifier of convection and non-convection is vertical velocity.
488 While dilute dCAPE is intended to capture more information than vertical velocity, such as heat and
489 moisture convergence, the dataset in this study shows that vertical velocity tends to be the dominant
490 link of dilute dCAPE to convection, and vertical velocity itself outperforms dilute dCAPE in the
491 ML trigger. There are similar results for the advective tendency of humidity (not shown).

492 *d. Convective Clusters and Uncertainty*

497 To further explore model explainability, SHAP values were calculated for the random forest for
498 each feature and event, before the SHAP values were clustered into six clusters using the k-means
499 algorithm. Figure 8 (top row) shows the clustering results in the SHAP value space for several
500 features. The scatters show distinctive clusters, which is expected since the k-means clustering was
501 performed on the SHAP values. The clustering tends to be more defined for the most important
502 features (e.g., ω mid, dilute dCAPE). Figure 8 also shows the same clusters, but in the real feature
503 space (bottom row: i.e., the actual atmospheric measurements used as predictors). Although the
504 data were clustered using the SHAP values, the groupings are still somewhat apparent in the real
505 feature space, which shows that the k-means clustering method still indirectly reflects the actual
506 environmental state.

510 Figure 9 shows the predicted unscaled probabilities and observed occurrence of convection for
511 each of the clusters. Even though the data were only clustered on the SHAP values, distinct
512 convective and non-convective groupings emerged, with an apparent split around a probability
513 of 0.5. Based on the narrower distributions of predicted probabilities near zero and the large
514 number of observed non-convective events, the 1st and 2nd clusters were characterized as certain
515 non-convective clusters. Based on the narrower distributions of probabilities near one and the
516 large number of observed convective events, the 5th and 6th clusters were identified as certain
517 convective clusters. In contrast, based on the large spread of probabilities between zero and the

493 FIG. 8. (a) Scatters of the clusters in SHAP value space for several features. Since the k-means clustering was
 494 performed on the SHAP values, the clusters show distinct groupings in the SHAP value scatterplots. (b) Scatters
 495 of the clusters in real feature space for several features. Although the k-means clustering was performed on the
 496 SHAP values, the groupings of the clusters are still apparent in the real feature scatterplots.

518 threshold, the 3rd cluster was characterized as an uncertain non-convective cluster. The 4th cluster
 519 was characterized as an uncertain convective cluster because of the large spread of probabilities
 520 between the threshold and one.

521 To further characterize each cluster, Figure 10 shows the average feature values and SHAP values
 522 for each cluster. The certain convective events (Clusters 5 and 6) have large upward (negative)
 523 vertical velocities that the ML model identifies as indicating a high probability of convection,
 524 such that the SHAP value associated with vertical velocity is large and positive. For these certain
 525 convective events, the model considers features other than vertical velocity and dilute dCAPE
 526 very little. In contrast, the uncertain convective events (Cluster 4) have a lower average upward
 527 vertical velocity and dilute dCAPE, and thus the model uses other features such as precipitable
 528 water, low-level temperature, and surface relative humidity to predict the occurrence of convection.
 529 Without dynamical forcing, the model is less certain about predicting convection.

507 FIG. 9. Histograms of the unscaled predicted probability of convection (left) and the observed occurrence of
 508 convection (right) for each of the clusters. The clustering created distinct convective and non-convective groups,
 509 with clusters mostly all above or below a probability of 0.5.

530 FIG. 10. Average characteristics for each cluster. The feature values (i.e., the actual atmospheric measurements
 531 which have been scaled) are on the top, and the corresponding SHAP values (i.e., the marginal contribution of
 532 each feature to the predicted probability) are on the bottom. The magnitude of the SHAP values for each cluster
 533 varies, as shown by the different x-axis scales in panel b.

534 For the certain non-convective events (Cluster 1 and 2), the model uses downward (positive)
535 or near-zero vertical velocity and low dilute dCAPE to predict a low probability of convection.
536 Cluster 1 mostly contains daytime events, when the surface temperatures, latent heat fluxes, and
537 sensible heat fluxes are usually higher. Cluster 2 mostly contains nighttime events, when the surface
538 temperatures, latent heat fluxes, and sensible heat fluxes are usually lower. However, despite these
539 cluster distinctions, the random forest primarily uses vertical velocity to predict the output for both.
540 Uncertain non-convective events (Cluster 3) have a small average upward vertical velocity, so the
541 model also relies on low-level temperature, surface relative humidity, and CIN to determine if the
542 case is non-convective.

543 These results are also reflected in Figure 8, where, for example in the bottom left panel, the certain
544 convective cases (Clusters 5 and 6) have a high upward vertical velocity. The uncertain events
545 (Clusters 3 and 4) have smaller, but still upward vertical velocities, but the uncertain convective
546 events (Cluster 4) tend to have higher precipitable water than the uncertain non-convective events
547 (Cluster 3).

548 Figure 11 shows SHAP dependence plots for vertical velocity, dilute dCAPE, precipitable water,
549 and low-level temperature. Each curve on the SHAP dependence plot shows the partial predicted
550 probability (or SHAP value) response as the feature value increases for each cluster. The certain
551 convective events (Clusters 5 and 6) show a distinct vertical velocity signal that is reflected in
552 the higher SHAP values and thus higher probabilities of convection. The SHAP dependence plot
553 for vertical velocity shows thresholding behavior, where events with vertical velocities exceeding
554 approximately -5 hPa hr^{-1} have a large positive contribution to the predicted probability. Even
555 though the uncertain convective events (Cluster 4) have similar vertical velocities as uncertain
556 non-convective events (Cluster 3), they have distinct curves in precipitable water and low-level
557 temperature, which differentiates them from non-convective events.

562 To sum up, using ML and SHAP value clustering, distinct convective groups can be produced
563 to cluster atmospheric events into certain and uncertain, convective and non-convective events.
564 These results show that strong upward vertical velocity helps to predict convective events with
565 greater certainty. If the vertical velocity is not strongly upward, then it is much less certain
566 whether convection will occur; for these cases, other features such as precipitable water, low-

558 FIG. 11. SHAP dependence plots for vertical velocity (ω mid), dilute dCAPE, precipitable water (PW), and
 559 low-level temperature (T low) for each of the clusters. The SHAP dependence plots for ω mid and dilute dCAPE
 560 show thresholding behavior, in which events with high vertical velocity magnitudes and high dCAPE have a large
 561 positive marginal contribution to the predicted probability.

567 level temperature, or surface relative humidity are essential in indicating whether events are likely
 568 convective or non-convective.

569 4. Discussion

570 Overall, the probabilistic random forest trigger outperforms conventional triggers and has similar
 571 performance to other non-probabilistic ML models. However, while the ARM variational analysis
 572 training dataset offered the advantage that it was consistent with precipitation observations, it was
 573 limited in that it only represents a single location, and is likely not generalizable to other regions.
 574 The simplistic precipitation threshold over the large region of approximately 3 degrees may not
 575 have captured the convective events thoroughly; it likely captured larger convective systems but
 576 limited the ability of the model to capture smaller convective storms. These limitations will be

577 explored in future work, using higher resolution, spatial datasets, and more refined definitions of
578 convection occurrence, for the probabilistic trigger to be able to perform well globally.

579 The explainability methods in this paper are specific to the given dataset; the feature rankings
580 don't inform us about the best overall features, but rather the best features among the ones available.
581 Additionally, correlations among features can dilute the feature importance and relevance values
582 of correlated features, but the grouped feature rankings help to reduce misinterpreting the feature
583 rankings due to correlations.

584 The probabilistic trigger in this study, with its well-represented diurnal cycle and robust reliability
585 curve, could be a promising direction for improving weather and climate models. For example,
586 the drizzle problem in GCMs may be alleviated with a probabilistic trigger that better captures the
587 diurnal cycle. Probabilistic predictions of precipitation in weather forecasting may become more
588 reliable with a more reliable convection trigger.

589 The ML approach used in this study allows us to consider a wide range of input features to
590 select the most important ones. The feature importance results generally agree with previous
591 studies, which show large-scale vertical velocity to be an important predictor of convection (Birch
592 et al. 2014; Peters et al. 2013). Vertical velocity is indicative of low-level convergence, which
593 can dynamically initiate convection. Convergence can also increase low-level moisture, which can
594 help to initiate and sustain convection. However, vertical velocity can also be a result of existing
595 convection, and this study does not establish a clear cause-and-effect relationship between vertical
596 velocity and convection.

597 The clustering approach shows results that are physically consistent with previous studies, but
598 also goes well beyond as we find clusters that are not well represented by typical triggers (e.g.,
599 dCAPE) alone. The characteristic clusters found in this study could be linked to different types of
600 convection. Future work will explore how certain and uncertain regimes correspond to different
601 types convection, such as synoptic-scale systems, which tend to be easier to predict an hour in
602 advance, or local instabilities that may be less predictable.

603 This study shows potential for a probabilistic ML trigger trained on a global convection dataset
604 to be implemented as a stochastic trigger in an operational model. To do this, convection would
605 trigger in each timestep if a random uniform number is less than the predicted probability from
606 the ML trigger for the given large-scale atmospheric state, unlike a deterministic thresholding

607 approach. The random number field would have spatial and temporal coherence, which also
608 provides an opportunity to represent memory in the convective lifecycle. Implementing the trigger
609 operationally would test the online performance, which is generally more challenging than achieving
610 good offline performance.

611 **5. Conclusion**

612 In this study, we applied explainable ML methods with a probabilistic random forest to better
613 understand how to predict the occurrence of deep atmospheric convection. The model was trained
614 using atmospheric inputs from the variational analysis over the Southern Great Plains. Clustering
615 of SHAP values derived from the random forest were used to interpret model uncertainty.

616 The model skill, as measured by precision, recall, F1 score, and Brier skill score, was better than
617 conventional CAPE-based triggers. This may indicate that considering more atmospheric variables
618 than a single CAPE-based threshold allows the trigger to better identify convective events. Vertical
619 velocity in the mid troposphere was found to be the most important feature in the random forest,
620 which suggests that the large-scale upward motion due to convergence plays an important role in
621 triggering an atmospheric instability. Dilute dCAPE, which was found to be the best convection
622 trigger in previous studies, primarily relies on vertical velocity to classify convective events, but is
623 less important than vertical velocity in the random forest.

624 Clustering of the SHAP values produced groupings of certain and uncertain, non-convective and
625 convective events. Certain convective events were characterized by large upward vertical veloc-
626 ities, while certain non-convective events were characterized by near-zero or downward vertical
627 velocities. Uncertain events had smaller upward vertical velocities but could be differentiated into
628 likely convective or likely non-convective events using other features such as precipitable water,
629 low-level temperature, or surface relative humidity.

630 This study showed that a probabilistic ML convection trigger may have the potential to be
631 used in operational models to significantly improve predictions of convection. Since a given
632 large-scale atmospheric state could correspond to multiple sub-grid convective (or non-convective)
633 states, the probabilistic framework used in this study allows for a better understanding of uncertain
634 atmospheric states. A probabilistic trigger like the one used in this study could be implemented as
635 a stochastic parameterization in the future.

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650 CC BY public copyright licence to any Author Accepted Manuscript (AAM) version arising from
651 this submission.

652 *Data availability statement.* The ARM variational analysis dataset used for this research
653 is available from <https://www.arm.gov/capabilities/science-data-products/vaps/varanal>. The
654 Python code for the machine learning training and evaluation in this study is available from
655 https://github.com/gretamiller/convection_trigger_SGP.

656 APPENDIX A

657 **Random Forest Hyperparameters**

658 The random forest has several hyperparameters controlling the architecture setup that can be
659 tuned to a given dataset, shown in Table A1. Bayesian optimization was used to tune the model
660 hyperparameters (using the Scikit-optimize package Pedregosa et al. (2012)). We used four-fold
661 cross-validation on the training set, splitting the 12-year training dataset into evaluation sets of 3
662 consecutive years to avoid any issues with temporal correlations. Like the original random forest,
663 the depth of the trees was not limited (Breiman 2001).

TABLE A1. Optimized random forest hyperparameters

Hyperparameter	Description	Search range	Optimized value
Tree density	number of individual trees that are averaged in the random forest	50-300	288
Max features	maximum number of environmental inputs that each tree can use	4-12	9
Min samples split	minimum number of samples required in a node to do another decision tree split	2-4	3
Min samples leaf	minimum number of samples that are required to be at a node	1-4	3

Note: Hyperparameter descriptions from Scikit-learn ML library for Python (Pedregosa et al. 2012)

APPENDIX B

Probability Scaling for Undersampled Dataset

To reduce the class imbalance, majority class undersampling was used, in which the majority class was randomly undersampled by a factor of $1/r$. Various undersampling ratios were tested, and undersampling by a factor of $r = 3$ (with a convective to non-convective ratio of 0.285) was chosen to optimize performance metrics on both the undersampled and original training datasets, using the same k-fold cross validation of the hyperparameter optimization. Since undersampling changes the frequency of positive events, the probabilities need to account for this change (Miloshevich et al. 2023).

Following the methods in Miloshevich et al. (2023), let $p_0(x)$ represent the probability of a non-convective event given that $X = x$ in the original dataset. Then the probability of a convective event is $p_1(x) = 1 - p_0(x)$. In the undersampled dataset, the probabilities of non-convective ($p'_0(x)$) and convection ($p'_1(x)$) are given as

$$p'_0(x) = \frac{\frac{1}{r}p_0(x)}{\frac{1}{r}p_0(x) + p_1(x)} \quad (\text{B1})$$

and

$$p'_1(x) = \frac{p_1(x)}{\frac{1}{r}p_0(x) + p_1(x)} \quad (\text{B2})$$

To get an estimate of the true probabilities, the equations above can be inverted to give

$$p_0(x) = \frac{r p'_0(x)}{1 - (1 - r)p'_0(x)} \quad (\text{B3})$$

684 FIG. C1. Elbow curve plot for k-means clustering of the SHAP values. Six clusters were chosen for the analysis
 685 since the within-cluster variance flattens as the number of clusters increases beyond six clusters.

679 and

$$p_1(x) = \frac{p'_1(x)}{r + (1-r)p'_1(x)} \quad (\text{B4})$$

680 The raw probabilities from the random forest predictions can then be tested on an original test set
 681 (not undersampled) after the probability rescaling (Equations B3 and B4).

682 APPENDIX C

683 K-Means Clustering

686 After training the random forest, the SHAP values were clustered using k-means clustering from
 687 the Scikit-learn ML library for Python (Pedregosa et al. 2012). The elbow method was used to
 688 determine the optimal number of clusters (Kodinariya and Makwana 2013). Figure C1 shows the
 689 within-cluster variance against the number of clusters. The number of clusters used in this study,
 690 $n=6$, was chosen where the decline in variance flattens with increasing number of clusters.

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